

METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LESSON

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Abstract. *This article describes the methodological possibilities of organizing extracurricular activities to improve the efficiency of knowledge of students in grades 7-8 of biology in secondary schools, the priority of using didactic, (problem, interactive) methods from modern pedagogical technologie*

Keywords: *extra-curricular and school activities, self-study, pedagogical conditions, form, method, means, biology, integrative approach, improvement, pedagogical and psychological process, efficiency.*

Introduction. It is based on the self-regulation and self-control of students under the guiding influence of the teacher in the organization of extracurricular activities in biology in grades 7-8 and in classrooms self-directed training in the library and at home should become the leading form. This includes the rational use of the material base of education: additional and reference literature, visual aids, didactic materials, technical tools in extracurricular work. It consists of:

- zoology and human health science, which includes various forms of working with textbooks and additional literature, providing theoretical knowledge acquisition;
- a system of tasks for independent work, in which experiments include performing creative work in specially equipped laboratories, designing tools, preparing mock-ups, models and others, is appropriate.

In the process of completing the tasks mentioned above, students work with tools following various manuals and safety rules they develop skills, learn to use didactic materials, they acquire the skills of attracting various information and supporting materials for self-examination. At the same time, they have the ability to choose the necessary materials for completing tasks, determine the sequence of work, take into account the time organizational skills are formed, such activities help students acquire the skills of working in conditions that are new to them, and the teacher helps students learn it allows to consistently form the qualities necessary for active participation in the educational process with a clear goal in mind. As a result, it will be possible to gradually introduce a new form of organizing educational activities for students - independent activities without a teacher in empty classrooms. It is built on the basis of self-regulation and self-control of students under the guiding influence of the teacher in the organization of extracurricular activities in grades 7-8, and in classrooms, independent training conducted in the library and at home on the basis of an individual plan should become the leading form. in the process of organizing independent training with 7th-8th-grade students it is important not to allow mental stress. For this purpose, it is necessary to form rational methods of educational work in children, to find a way in the flow of scientific, social and political information, to conduct independent experiments and to conduct observations. It is important to take into account that independent training can be carried out when

the independence of students is at different levels, which, of course, will undoubtedly affect the formation of their personality. Some students understand the tasks before them and the ways to solve them much better. Children work without the help of an educator, the intervention of an educator is not acceptable here, because such a situation has the greatest opportunity to form children's diligence and knowledge needs. Subordinate-independent situation arises when the student acts independently, but depends on the opinion and assessment of education. Even if the work is done with interest and enthusiasm, there are aspects of insecurity in the actions of a child who is doing independent work. In each of the indicated cases, it is necessary to involve students in the learning process, to rely on their interests, to allow students to feel success in their educational activities, to encourage them and, of course, to teach them to study. Observations show that the educators themselves often do not know the diversity of children's independent preparation and their relationship to work. And the teacher, relying on the manifestation of such situations, can implement a better individual approach, and during the period of independent training, he can turn the coordination and comparison of his influence on the students into an effective means of personality formation.

The object and methods of the research: the process of improvement of extracurricular activities was organized for the 7th-8th grade students of the 18th general secondary school in the Termiz city, Surkhandarya region. In the 7-8th grades of general education, the forms, methods, tools and experimental tests of the improvement of extracurricular activities were carried out. The purpose of the research is to develop a system for improving extracurricular activities in grades 7-8 and to create scientific-methodical recommendations. Scientific theoretical justification that improvement of extracurricular activities in 7-8th grades is an urgent pedagogical problem; literature on the improvement of extracurricular activities in the 7-8th grades, methodical possibilities of improving didactic and extracurricular activities in science teaching, modern educational technologies (problematic, interactive) improvement of usage priorities;- Use of effective forms, methods and means of improving extracurricular work in 7-8th grades; - Development of conclusions, proposals and recommendations based on the results of experiments conducted in the 7-8th grades on the improvement of extracurricular activities. The results of the research and its discussion: Conclusions, suggestions and recommendations were developed based on the results of the experiment-test conducted in the 7-8th grades on the improvement of extracurricular activities. The fact that improvement of extracurricular work in biology in 7-8th grades is an urgent pedagogical problem was based on scientific theory; As a result of the conducted scientific and theoretical studies, it became clear that the possibilities of improving extracurricular activities in the 7th-8th grades have not been thoroughly researched. Description of the methodology used in the research: scientific-pedagogical base competence approach to the researched problem, use of a set of methods corresponding to its purpose, task and practical assumptions, experimental and testing fields.

In conclusion, the current state of integration of biological education, pedagogical conditions have been determined, and the leading form, method, tool and information competencies have been systematized. Research methods used in the course of the lesson 7-8th grade to study and analyze scientific and methodical literature, programs, textbooks, educational and methodical manuals on the problem of improving extracurricular activities in biology classes of students; monitoring and summarizing lessons; conducting and analyzing interviews with teachers and students, questionnaires, tests, blitz questions, written - control work. 7th-8th grade

students in biology lessons outside the classroom the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of improving work, the development of a system of improving extracurricular activities to increase the lesson efficiency of 7-8th grade students in biology, as well as creating scientific and methodological recommendations, teaching young biology teachers to perform extracurricular activities for 7th-8th grade students there will be methodical support in external ethics.

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